

HEALTH INNOVATION NEXT GENERATION PAYMENT & PRICING MODELS (HI-PRIX):
Balancing Sustainability of Innovation with Sustainability of Health Care

M12 Open database with detailed mapping of policies and incentive mechanisms to foster pharmaceutical innovation and access to innovation

WP7 Incentives for pharmaceutical innovation and equitable access to innovation

Authors:

Centre for Health Economics & Policy Innovation, Imperial College

London (ICL), UK:

Professor Marisa Miraldo

Professor Mujaheed Shaikh

Dr Chuanzi Yue

Institute for Interdisciplinary Innovation in healthcare (I3h), Université

Libre de Bruxelles (ULB), Belgium:

Professor Hilde Stevens

Professor Mathias Dewatripont

Professor Michel Goldman

Xixian Niu, MSc

Shiri Mermelstein, MSc

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Project Acronym	HI-PRIX
Project Title	Health Innovation Next Generation Payment & Pricing Models: Balancing Sustainability of Innovation with Sustainability of Health Care
Project Coordinator	Oriana Ciani oriana.ciani@unibocconi.it
Grant Agreement number	101095593
Project Duration	January 2023 – December 2025 (36 months)
Deliverable No.	Milestone 12: Open database with detailed mapping of policies and incentive mechanisms to foster pharmaceutical innovation and access to innovation
Work Package	WP7 Incentives for pharmaceutical innovation and equitable access to innovation
Task	Release of the baseline policy mapping conducted under Task 7.1 (<i>"Preparatory work: Incentives for pharmaceutical innovation"</i>) completed in M16 (April 2024) in an open access repository aligned with the completion of WP7 deliverables 7.1 (M30) and 7.2 (M36)
Lead Beneficiary	ICL, ULB
Status	Final
Dissemination level	Public
Type	Milestone report
Due date of deliverable	31 December 2025
Actual submission date	31 December 2025
Author(s) & Organization(s)	ICL: Professor Marisa Miraldo, Professor Mujaheed Shaikh Dr Chuanzi Yue, Dr Arianna Gentilini ULB: Professor Hilde Stevens, Professor Mathias Dewatripont Xixian Niu, MSc, Shiri Mermelstein, MSc
Reviewer(s) & Organization(s)	Consortium (all)
Contact	m.miraldo@imperial.ac.uk ; hstevens@i3health.eu

Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Term
AMC	Advance Market Commitment
AMR	Antimicrobial Resistance
CMNN	Communicable, Maternal, Neonatal and Nutritional diseases
COVAX	COVID-19 Vaccines Global Access Facility
DALYs	Disability-Adjusted Life Years
EMA	European Medicines Agency
GAVI	Gavi, the Vaccine Alliance
GBD	Global Burden of Disease
HICs	High-Income Countries
HII	Horizontal Inequity Index
IHI	Innovative Health Initiative
IHME	Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation
IMI	Innovative Medicines Initiative
IP	Intellectual Property
NCDs	Non-Communicable Diseases
NDs	Neglected Diseases
NIH	National Institutes of Health
PRIME	PRiority MEdicines
PPP	Public–Private Partnership
PRV	Priority Review Voucher
R&D	Research and Development
WHO	World Health Organization
WP	Work Package

Glossary

Term	Lay Definition
Incentive Mechanisms	<p>The underlying economic design features of policy interventions that enter firms' intertemporal R&D profit-maximisation problem as distinct arguments of the expected payoff function, rather than to the policy instruments themselves. Formally, they are the micro-level channels through which public policy impacts the firm's strategy by altering (i) the cost and risk profile of R&D investment, (ii) the timing and volatility of expected cash flows, (iii) the information set and coordination environment, and (iv) the conditions under which rents from successful innovation can be appropriated or must be shared. In this framework, a given policy instrument is conceptualised as a bundle of incentive mechanisms, each of which has a potentially distinct marginal effect on R&D strategy. Analytically, these mechanisms are treated as the primitive units of analysis, because they map more directly to the structural parameters that govern firms' dynamic R&D choices than do coarse instrument labels (such as "push" or "pull").</p>
Pull Incentives	<p>Policy instruments that act on the revenue side of the firm's R&D decision problem, by increasing the expected net present value (NPV) of successful projects. Economically, pull incentives raise the expected payoff conditional on success or expand the effective size or price of the market. They therefore operate by strengthening demand for innovation outputs, shifting the expected return distribution rather than the cost of effort.</p>
Push Incentives	<p>Policy instruments that act on the cost side of the firm's R&D decision problem, by subsidising inputs or sharing downside risk. Economically, push incentives lower the marginal and/or fixed cost of R&D, thereby shifting the firm's R&D supply curve outward. They primarily affect the ex-ante expected cost and risk profile of projects, without directly conditioning transfers on realised market success.</p>
Neglected Diseases	<p>Diseases that mainly affect low- and middle-income settings and have historically received limited private R&D investment because expected commercial returns are weak. Based on Gad et al. 2025, neglected diseases include: HIV/AIDS; tuberculosis; malaria; diarrhoeal diseases (rotavirus, cholera, shigella, cryptosporidiosis, enterotoxigenic/enteroaggregative E. coli, giardiasis); kinetoplastid diseases (human African trypanosomiasis/sleeping sickness, leishmaniasis, Chagas disease); severe bacterial infections (pneumococcal pneumonia/meningitis, meningococcal meningitis); salmonella infections (typhoid, paratyphoid, non-typhoidal Salmonella enterica); helminth infections (schistosomiasis, onchocerciasis, lymphatic filariasis, tapeworm, hookworm, whipworm, roundworm, strongyloidiasis); and other rare or neglected tropical diseases (dengue, hepatitis B, hepatitis C, leprosy, cryptococcal meningitis, snakebite envenoming, Buruli ulcer, trachoma, leptospirosis, rheumatic fever, mycetoma, chikungunya, dracunculiasis/guinea worm, rabies, scabies, yaws).</p>
Rare Diseases	<p>Diseases affecting small patient populations, identified at the indication level using Cortellis and Orphanet prevalence thresholds (e.g. <1 in 2,000 in the EU, <200,000 patients in the US).</p>

Overview

of novel pharmaceuticals adopted or implemented between **2000 and 2022** across a sample of **42 countries**. To support the set of analyses conducted under WP7, we constructed a comprehensive cross-country dataset building on the policy mapping conducted as part of **Task 7.1**, proprietary data sources (Dimensions.AI scientific research database and Clarivate's Cortellis Drug Discovery Intelligence), and public data obtained from the World Bank, OECD and official websites. We select a sample of 42 countries that together account for over 88% of clinical trial activity globally over the sample period. This includes all EU and European Economic Area (EEA) countries, the UK, and Switzerland, along with other major pharmaceutical markets (US, Canada, Australia, Japan, South Korea) and BRICS economies (Brazil, Russia, India, China, and South Africa), reflecting their growing role in global pharmaceutical innovation.

For each country, we mapped policy incentives for biomedical innovation (excluding medical devices) adopted between 2000 and 2022. Our open policy data sample comprises key supply-push incentives, including Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs), and expenditure-based fiscal incentives for R&D, and several demand-pull instruments, including income-based fiscal incentives, Advance Market Commitments (AMCs), expedited regulatory programmes, and transferable Priority Review Vouchers (PRVs). Each policy was mapped to all disease and public health priority areas eligible for the incentive. The raw policy corpus includes 310 PPPs, 4 AMC programmes, 40 expenditure-based fiscal schemes, 24 income-based fiscal schemes, 36 expedited regulatory programmes, 3 PRVs, and 30 specific HTA paths.

Table 1. Policy definitions

Policy incentive	Definition
Public-Private Partnerships	A collaboration within consortia formed by private and public organizations to pool expertise across diverse stakeholders to deliver an agreed output within a certain period of time.
Expenditure-based fiscal incentives	Horizontal tax policies that offer deductions or credits for R&D expenses, irrespective of project targets or likelihood of success, based on the premise that firms are best positioned to identify research domains with commercial prospects.
Income-based fiscal incentives	Relief mechanisms that reduce tax rates on income derived from R&D activities (IP licenses and revenues from patent-protected products).
Advanced Market Commitments	An upfront commitment made by donor countries or multilateral health organizations to purchase a product once it has been successfully developed, typically for a predefined number of units at a fixed price per dose.
Expedited Regulatory Programmes	A designation granted by regulatory agencies to qualifying drug candidates, offering shorter assessment timelines, earlier submission of evidence, adjusted evidence requirements, and scientific advice (e.g., on defining endpoints or biomarker measurements), along with frequent interactions with regulators.
Priority Review Vouchers	A tradable voucher granted by regulatory agencies to qualifying drug candidates, allowing an accelerated approval process for both the drug it is awarded to and another therapeutic product of choice, which can be sold to other developers.

Data structure and classification

The open policy dataset provides a structured mapping of pharmaceutical innovation policy incentives implemented between 2000 and 2022. Each policy in our sample corresponds to a distinct legislative, regulatory, fiscal, or programmatic intervention adopted by a public authority or

philanthropic organisation and is associated with a specific country (or, where applicable, a political group or group of countries). Policies are dated using five year time bins, reflecting the period of introduction or establishment, to support consistent comparison over time. Policies are classified along several dimensions capturing both institutional and public health relevance. These include the type of incentive, the decision-making body responsible for the policy, and its alignment with defined public health priority areas. Disease focus is recorded using broad clinical groupings, alongside indicators capturing equity dimensions such as rarity (rare vs non-rare) and geographic focus (for example neglected tropical diseases, NTDs, vs non-NTDs). Each policy may be mapped to multiple disease areas where eligibility applies.

Table 2. Variable definition

Field	Description
Country or political group	National jurisdiction(s) or political entity implementing or participating in the policy, including individual countries, multi-country partnerships, territories, and regional or supranational groupings.
Incentive type	Policy instrument category (e.g. AMCs)
Incentive name	Official name of the policy or programme
Decision-making body	Institution(s) responsible for policy design, implementation
Period (introduction or establishment)	Policy introduction timing recorded in five year bins
Disease type	Classified by the broadest Global Burden of Disease categories: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communicable, Maternal, Neonatal, and Nutritional (CMNN) diseases • Non-communicable diseases (NCDs)
Public health priority area	Priority health domain targeted by the policy <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Neglected tropical diseases; • Emerging infectious diseases; • Antimicrobial resistance; • Rare and ultra-rare diseases; • Oncology; • End-of-life conditions; • Neurodegenerative conditions; • Mental Health; • Paediatric diseases; • Women’s health; • Vaccines; • Regenerative medicine; • Generic medicines.
Rarity	Classification of targeted conditions as rare or non-rare
Geography	Indicator of relevance to neglected tropical diseases (NTD vs non-NTD)
References	Links to official documents and public sources

Open data and visualisation

The dataset shared on **Flourish** presents the policy mapping in a **descriptive and exploratory format**. Users can search through the policy incentives by country, incentive type, decision-making body, time period, and public health priority area. The data is also available for download (csv format) via **Zenodo**.

Relation to other WP7 outputs and intended use

The policy mapping provides the basis for the analytical work conducted under WP7. The open dataset is intended to support transparency, comparative policy analysis, and informed discussion among policymakers, researchers, and other stakeholders interested in pharmaceutical innovation and access. By making the policy landscape visible in a harmonised and comparable way, it contributes to the “evidence for policy” approach promoted under the EU’s Horizon Europe missions and the WHO’s Global Observatory on Health R&D.

Table 3. Data collection methods

Incentives	Time period	Desk research	Existing database	Validation method
Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs)	1990-2023	Academic literature, official websites, and documents from 310 PPPs	Consortiapedia	Online survey (n=5)
Advance Market Commitments (AMCs)	2007-2022	Desk research: official websites/annual reports (GAVI, COVAX, WHO)	UNICEF Covid-19 vaccines dashboard	
Fiscal - Expenditure	2000-2022	Academic literature	OECD R&D tax incentives	
Fiscal - Income	2000-2022	Academic literature and annual reports from consulting firms; ChatGPT 4 with Bing plugin	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> OECD IP Regime database Bloomberg BNA’s BEPS tracker 	
Expedited Regulatory Programmes Priority Review Vouchers (PRVs)	1997 - 2023	Official websites and documents		